

Current Literary Process and Analysis of Works in a New Style

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Annotation:

The works related to the current literary process and their analysis, the different aspects of the works that are characteristic of a special style and suitable from the Shura literature are revealed. The current problems and inner experiences of the works of today are discussed. Brief analyzes of the important aspects of the analysis of the works, the realistic actions of the characters, the idea of the work, and the beautiful examples of the literature of the new era created on the basis of the sequence of thoughts in a new style.

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The achievements of the period of independence, a novel in a new way, a story, were able to provide a good foundation in the creation of stories. A huge number of achievements have been achieved using widely revealed opportunities. At the same time, drastic changes have occurred in our modern literature. An example of free creativity arose, in which the creators completely escaped the limit of restriction from real, life thoughts, concealment, inability to convey free thoughts to the reader. They began to write dangerously with new ideas and interpretations about the Black Days of the past, True Religion, true life. Not only in prose works, but also in the world of poetry a new style, genres were embodied.

In Independence literature, the novel "Olaboji" by Shukur Kholmirezayev, the story "Bulut tusgan oy", "Sho'rodan qolgan odamlar" by Shoyim Botayev, the story "Darvesh", the novel "Otamdan qolgan dalalar" by Togay Murad, Nazar Eshonqul's "Maymun yetaklagan odam", Luqman Boukhon's "Jaziramadagi odamlar", "Shamolni tutib bo'lmaydi" covered all literature.

It is clear that what he wanted to say when we read these works at first remains dark in the human mind. But when we read and reflect again, we witness how close works written in such a new style are to a person's life, the image of the real psyche, the harmonization of nationalism. And when

revealing the idea of novels, mostly retrospective and associative plots are used, and as such, their wide potential is used when interpreting the inner world of heroes, the experiences of the soul. For example, if we take a look at Nazar Eshonkul's "Maymun yetaklagan odam", first of all the title in this work is thought of by man. Why exactly this name? A reader who rushes to read the inside of the work cannot forgive this. But a carefully read person will realize how much a work is suitable for the title, that one title has occupied the entire content of the work and has a deep meaning. Focusing on the concise content of the work, we realize that from the very beginning of the work, the image of the old man embodied an unusual pathos. The events of the work began with an exposition. The hero of the work describes the image of an old man who, all his life, spent his time, his all-round intelligence on the affairs of the government, was not rewarded accordingly, spending all his skills to work, without focusing on his health, his important work. As a result, the old man, left with old age and strength, became an unnecessary person. His wife and the children were abandoned. Bright pictures at the time of the flowering of the old man's life, which expressed his life by drawing a variety of paintings, but in solitude he paints colorless ones. The old man embodied his whole life in two pictures. In the first picture, the monkey is led by a young man, a young man with a chain around his neck, and in the second, the opposite. The first picture is a symbol of youth. While working in responsible duties, the wrongs, were periods of struggle against evils, gradually is reflected in the second picture, in which these evils triumph over humanity, and the world of mankind gets used to the most difficult things from this over the years. The monkey is a symbol of evil. As the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov said: "no society can imagine its prospects without developing and strengthening its spiritual and moral values in the minds of people." [1.36 page] First of all, it is necessary to educate people in society. The content of the idea that wants to be revealed in this work also goes back to this sentence. It is also a big problem that people constantly live in life thinking about themselves, not being hurt by someone. By the way, affection and love play a big role in the world. The old also in the work gave the affection as much as human beings, but she herself could not return, and gradually understood that but it was too late in her.

The novel genre took its first step towards its flourishing in the 19th century. Major manifestations of the art of critical realism, such as Stendal, Balzac, Dickens, Turgenev, Pushkin, Lev Tolstoy, played a large role in the development of the genre. The novel is a new genre in the history of Uzbek literature. A literary figure who has adapted the fundamental book "Uzbek novel" by Professor Mirvaliyev will have a perfect understanding of the birth and formation of the novel genre in Uzbek literature.

"Each nation experienced its renaissance in its own way," A. Losev and emphasizes that since the beginning signs of Renaissance art, there is an increase in thirst for ancient values. [2] We also have a habit of approaching works from a different method today. The situation in which the people are in a difficult situation, seen firsthand but no action is taken, is also evident in the novel "Otamdan qolgan dalalar" by Togai Murad. The 100-year-old past of the entire Uzbek people was reflected by the typical image of the Uzbek peasants through the image of a simple, hardworking peasant. It embodies many years of folk hardships created through styles typical of the modern novel. The heroes of the novel are representatives of the common people, who love and awaken their land like their child. They will only strive for work, for the people. In response, to this, they are subjected to a rain of oppression and sufferings. At such a time, they do not believe that these problems in life, the plagues rained down by the invaders, the slanders are being done by human beings. Agrab, dissatisfied with the politics of the Tsarist government from an early age, influenced by the spirit of hatred of militarism, in which the rapes are growing, walks in the hope of revenge on such a gang. Their hatred was born in the Natina of the teasing stones, which are being made in return for the love of the heroes for the land, trust in people, love for work. The spirit of the spiritually and materially oppressed people faded. The hero is tortured in various ways in return for

years of hard work on the government, the stones of allegation are thrown and imprisoned for eight years. The image of a simple son of a hardworking people, whose shoulders were not seen off, is clearly expressed. Togai Murad comments on this work: "I will put a monument to the Uzbek people with this work".

Nowadays, religious themes are also focused on precisely. In the samples of literature of previous years, the concepts of religious philosophical, moral themes, educational norms calling to religion, which were not previously encountered, were practically not used. In our new modern literature, religious views are slow to be pursued. For Example. We witness that there are several religious poems in the series of Oripov's "Haj daftari" and "Hikmat sadolari". In fact, we know very well that our religion is a criterion that calls people every day to good, to a dishonest faith, to morality. Through the works, the poems of this series showed the calling of the youth to the right path. In reality, ignorance of religion becomes a factor in the various evil vices. In this way, actions, activities, articles were not previously clearly expressed. And the introduction of such innovations into our current literature is becoming more popular. New works created in this time, when word masculinity is achieved, through our literature today, works, poems, stories and short stories flourishes.

Let's take a look at another novel written in fresh zinc. This work is a new age novel of the New Age, written in a unique style and with a unique new tone. In the novel, the lyrics and the tragedy are harmonized together. In the dramatic tour, too, tragicomedy available. The hero in the novel expresses the image of a dreamer who is not like everyone else a brave young man who always lives with his own dreams whose language comes out as death and is never afraid of death.

The novel "Qo'rqma" is a novel that is full of excitement. The fantasies of the hero who set out in search of students who went to Germany for the benefit of the people in order to clarify, compare the desires of dreams with the marriage of young people of the present time. From young people who do not feel the pain of the surrounding Homeland, traitor walks out dissatisfied with the ignorant traitors. His imagination is seventy students who have always gone with the grief of the motherland, the land. Opening the nation's eyes will be in the illusion of awakening. The work embodied history, honor, treason, kindness and love. The Fatherland depicts seventy students who did not return to study for the pain, as if it were a Vanishing Island. Just as the Aral Sea is lost, they disappear without a trace, without a reason. "O my country of resurrection is a trust in us, a trust in it, and a betrayal of it." [3] The novel was completed with such an appeal. Finding and reading the truth of works in which truth is embedded in the basis of the work is a very important issue. This work, which has just entered the stages of literature, will give the reader a deep thought. A novel written on the basis of historical fact 2021 year was considered the "book of the year".

One of Uzbekistan's enlightened creators, Chulpan, at the age of 16, wrote the book "Adabiyot nadur?" in his article, literature as a whole showed the following words about the world of creativity. "Yes, acting without stopping, our stagnant body, our body need water how much air is needed, so much literature is also needed for our soul, which is soiled with all sorts of black days on the way to life. If lives literature, the nation lives. The nation, whose literature has not died, and which has not cultivated the nobility, will one day be deprived of emotion, thought, thought, and a slow slow crisis". [4.36-37 page]

In fact, literature is not a set of dry ideas, but a perfect phenomenon, closely related to the inner experiences, psyche of mankind. Here are the different literary examples that have seen the World Summer by now many. We saw an analysis of three works created on the basis of the current literary process. Their approach in a new spirit was very effective and was able to attract readers much more. Free coverage of the problems of the day were able to freely file from the date of stay, and high results were achieved.

If I finish the end of the word through the content of the literary critic Umarali Normatov. “ One of the most important characteristics of the literary process in us in recent years is that our literature is becoming more diverse....we also have works belonging to a philosophically diverse direction, based on the heads of appearance” “[P.5.112] what true thoughts.

References.

1. I.Karimov O‘zbekiston XXI asr bo‘lag‘asida xavfsizlikka tahdid,barqarorlik shartlari va taraqqiyot kafolatlari Toshkent O‘zbekiston 1997yil 36 bet
2. Hozirgi adabiy jarayon majmua.
3. J.Jovliyev “Qo‘rqma” asari
4. Cho‘lpon Adabiyot nadur? ”Cho‘lpon” 1994 yil 36-37 betlar.
5. U. Normatov Umidbaxsh tamoyillar Toshkent “Ma‘naviyat” 2000 yil 112 bet

References

1. I. Karimov Threats to security, conditions of stability and guarantees of development of Uzbekistan at the threshold of the 21st century, Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 1997, 36 pages
2. The current literary process is complex.
3. J. Jovliyev’s work “Don’t be afraid”.
4. What is Cholpon Literature? “Cholpon” 1994 pp. 36-37.
5. U. Normatov Umidbakhsh principles Tashkent “Spirituality” 2000 112 pages